

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF ANTHROPOMETRY IN THE HISTORICAL ASPECT

Abdullayev A.,

*Head of Department, Associate Professor, Ph.D. in Medicine,
Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Human Anatomy and Medical Terminology,
Azerbaijan, Baku*

Allahverdiyeva N.,

*Assistant, Ph.D. in Medicine, Azerbaijan Medical University,
Department of Human Anatomy and Medical Terminology*

Mamedova A.

*Assistant, Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Human Anatomy and Medical Terminology
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Abstract

The development of anthropometry is touched on from a historical perspective. It has been noted that anthropometry has a deep connection with the exact sciences and arts. The contributions of various scientists, artists, and sculptors to the development of anthropometry were discussed.

Keywords: anthropometry, body height, canons.

Anthropometry gives us the factual basis for studying a person's appearance, teaching us how to measure the human body and determine the relationships between its parts. Thus, anthropometry represents only the technical part of somatic anthropology, which studies the human body, not only in its appearance but also in all its physiological functions [1, 2]. A study of the literature showed that interest in the morphometry of the skull, pelvis, and limbs has been renewed. This is due primarily to the spread of new research methods in anthropological work and the formation of a new scientific view of human physical capabilities. Indicators of the level of physical development are one of the objects of anthropology research. Their study is mainly possible using indexes. Anthropometry as a field of science has indeed expanded, moving beyond its classical framework and adopting a causal direction. In other words, now anthropometric measurements carried out among a certain segment of the population—individual ethnic groups, conscripts, teenage girls, and other groups—are aimed at explaining one or another of the obtained indicators and not at a purely “mechanical” process. It should be noted that the physical characteristics of a person, the degree of his development, and the types of body structure have been of interest since ancient times. This is natural because it was at this time, which was a period of early development in science and art, that the definition of standards of beauty and health came to the fore. It is clear that beauty as a subjective category was assessed in different ways at different times and according to different indicators. However, scientists, sculptors, and artists of antiquity had to make some, at least primitive, calculations; that is, these indicators, of course, could not “fall out of thin air”; the empirical factor even then played a role.

Hippocrates (460–370 BC) and Aristotle (384–322 BC) touched upon the connection between the structure and shape of the body and various physiological and mental problems. Hippocrates noted that obese people live shorter lives and women become infertile.

Archimedes determined the physical properties of objects by immersing them in liquid. The hydrostatic densitometry method, which is used to study the composition of the human body, is actually based on Archimedes' law.

But knowledge or canons that reflect reality (canon means reed, which is a sign that reed is used for measurements during construction work) are based on observations and calculations made on a living person. The study of these canons shows that they are based on two basic principles.

The first principle is based on the size of any part of the body not separated from other parts; another principle is based on the selection and segmentation of a particular part of the body (especially a joint), which is considered a unit of calculation. Of course, if we approach this issue from the anthropological position that interests us, we must reveal the following historical facts: The oldest of these laws is the so-called Egyptian grid system. Here, the distance from the foot to the ankle was taken as the basic module, $21 \frac{1}{4}$ times of which fell on the entire body. It is believed that the Egyptian grid system was considered and used by ancient sculptors for a long period of time. In a relatively late period in Egypt, the length of the middle finger of the hand was already accepted; it has been calculated that its length is $\frac{1}{19}$ that of the body.

The second principle is based on the classical canons, where the unit of measurement (in the literature, it is also called a module) was the naturally dissected parts of the body. This principle was formed in ancient Greece, starting in the 5th century BC. Probably the earliest and most widespread of the classical canons was put forward by Polycleus. As a module, I took the width of the palm at the level of the base of the fingers. Doryphoros and Diadumen are his famous works. The point is that during the time of Polycleus, wealthy customers wanted to see in their homes statues of figures that resembled their own and not divine beings accord-

ing to their beliefs. This created the need to study anatomy; the body dimensions of a real person and the ratio of these dimensions to each other were important. In the works of Polycleus, the face is 1/10 of the body, the head is 1/8, and the head and neck are 1/6.

Later, some changes were made to this law by Lysippos. Lysippos reflected these changes in the statue of Apoxyomene. In the Middle Ages, Byzantine laws were used more in the description of the physical structure of the human body; they were based on the natural expression of the body. According to them, the height of the face is 1/9 of the height of the body.

During the Renaissance, Leonardo da Vinci brought many innovations to the knowledge of the relationship of body parts to each other [3]. First of all, it is a question of the ratio of the height to the length of the arms when they are open to the sides. Long before him, Vitruvius (1st century BC) believed that these two dimensions were equal to each other. In the literature, this is called the "square of the ancients".

Da Vinci placed this figure in a circle, raised the arms slightly, and moved the legs apart. The center of the circle coincides with the umbilical ring. If we place a hexagon in a circle and pass two diameters, one vertical and the other horizontal, then in the middle of the latter is the umbilical ring, and the vertical diameter divides the body into two symmetrical parts. The distal parts of the arms and legs are located at the two upper and two lower angles of the hexagon. An interesting fact is that da Vinci personally never wanted to exhibit this picture. This picture was accidentally found in his pocketbook; apparently, the author drew the sketch as a kind of "draft" for himself. As the basic "unit of measurement" or module, da Vinci adopted the height of the head. According to him, this height is 1/8 of the body height.

A little different from Da Vinci, Michelangelo took the physiognomic height of the face, not the head, as a module and divided it into three parts. These parts correspond to the forehead, nose, and mouth-chin. In

the 18th and 19th centuries, the formation of anthropology as a biological field and the strengthening of the position of statistics in scientific research made it possible to explain the relationships of human body parts to each other on a scientific basis.

One of the first such explanations belongs to Kolman. The principle of dividing his body into parts is called the decimal system (translated as ten). According to this system, the height of the head is 13% of the body height; the trunk is 52–53% of the body height; the legs are 47%; and the arms are 44% of the body height. That is, the system is based on the percentage expression of the ratio of the body parts to the height of the neck.

Adolph Zeising was a German philosopher, poet, and mathematician who lived in the 19th century. He formulated the principles of mathematical aesthetics for the first time and claimed that beauty is not a subjective value but a precise form. According to the concept of *Der Goldene Schnitt*, Zeising divided the whole into two unequal parts; in this case, the ratio of the large part to the dimensions of the whole was like the ratio of the small part to the large part. This principle quickly took root in both sculpture and painting [4].

Thus, since its inception, anthropometry has had an important impact on the development of the sciences and arts by seriously integrating with them.

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